

KATRD *HYBRID* *CONFERENCE*

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE 2021

THE 132nd CONGRESS OF
THE KOREAN ACADEMY OF
TUBERCULOSIS AND
RESPIRATORY DISEASES

Nov. 11 THU - 12 FRI, 2021

LOTTE HOTEL WORLD, SEOUL, KOREA

**Breathe Better,
Live Better**

WELCOME MESSAGE

Dear Colleagues,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, it is our great pleasure to welcome you to the 2021 Korean Academy of Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases International Conference (KATRDIC 2021) in conjunction with the 132nd Congress of the KATRD in Seoul, Korea from November 11 to 12, 2021.

As witnessed last year, COVID-19 posed big challenges for us all. Even so, we persevered and were able to put forth a ground-breaking conference and ensured the continued progress of our field thanks to your unwavering support, patience and understanding. We had hoped to meet our many global colleagues in-person this year, but prudence has led us to opt for a hybrid platform. Nevertheless, I am confident that KATRDIC 2021 will be another memorable conference.

Under this year's theme "Breathe Better, Live Better," world-renowned invited speakers, chairs, and presenters will be the conduit for their latest innovations and insights taking place in the Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases field. As you look through the schedule, note that all times are listed in Korea Standard Time (GMT+9), so please be sure to adjust your schedule accordingly.

I would like to convey our sincere gratitude to the members of the KATRDIC committee, chairs, and presenters for their tireless efforts in making this conference a success.

Thank you again for your participation and welcome to KATRDIC 2021!

O Jung Kwon
President

The Korean Academy of Tuberculosis
and Respiratory Diseases

Jae Jeong Shim
Chairman of the Board of Trustees

The Korean Academy of Tuberculosis
and Respiratory Diseases

ORAL PRESENTATION 4

OP 4-4

Will There Be a Permanent Problem with Tuberculosis in Future Due to the Second Category of Patients in Serbia

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Background

The second category of tuberculosis (TB) patients present a tremendous problem for each subsequent treatment of tuberculosis and for society. The possibility of the appearance of resistant forms among these patients is more certain nowadays. The aim of this study was to analyze the possible problems that influence the Results of therapy among patients who belong to the second category.

Methods

This research included a 16-year period (from 2005 to 2020) at the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina (Serbia). The effects of treatment were evaluated using univariate and multivariate logistic regression analysis.

Results

There were 223 treated patients in the second category; 17.1% of them were without elementary school education. Almost 50% were unemployed, while every fifth patient was an alcoholic or socially disadvantaged (compared to newly registered $p=0.029$). In the group of 45-64 years of age, there were 2/3 (149) of patients. Every third patient was treated for TB in youth, while 12% were treated for TB in the previous year. Most patients in this category had previous TB treatment - once (195, 87.4%) or twice (23, 10.3%). Extended regimens were implemented in almost 23% of patients (compared to newly registered $p=0.018$), while interrupted treatment as an outcome was observed in 21.3% of patients ($p=0.008$). Independent predictors for belonging to the second category were patients with/without elementary school (RR 1.278; 95% CI (1.108 - 2.573); $p=0.032$) and patients with alcoholic abuse (RR 2.806; 95% CI (1.683-4.758); $p=0.029$). Multivariate analysis identified the level of education as an independent predictor for being in the second category.

Conclusions

Vulnerable populations who were previously treated for TB need continuous monitoring with the aim of preventing resistant forms of the disease.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Treatment Outcome, Category